

NUTRACEUTICALS IN THE ERA OF INNOVATION: MARKET INSIGHTS, AI INTEGRATION, AND MOLECULAR DOCKING APPROACHES

Vaishnavi S. Patil^{1*}, Ishwari S. Sutar², Akanksha S. Reke³, Dr. Sadhana R. Shahi⁴

^{1*,2,3}Student, Department of Pharmaceutics, Government College of Pharmacy karad, Maharashtra, 415124.

⁴Associate Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, Government College of Pharmacy.

Article Received on 23 Sept. 2025,
Article Revised on 13 October 2025,
Article Published on 01 Nov. 2025,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17471129>

*Corresponding Author

Vaishnavi S. Patil

Student, Department of Pharmaceutics,
Government College of Pharmacy
karad, Maharashtra, 415124.

How to cite this Article: Vaishnavi S. Patil^{1*}, Ishwari S. Sutar², Akanksha S. Reke³, Dr. Sadhana R. Shahi⁴ (2025). 'NUTRACEUTICALS IN THE ERA OF INNOVATION: MARKET INSIGHTS, AI INTEGRATION, AND MOLECULAR DOCKING APPROACHES' World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 14(11), 129–166.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Nutraceuticals, a fusion of "nutrition" and "pharmaceuticals," are food-derived products that offer health benefits beyond basic nutrition. They play a crucial role in disease prevention, health promotion, and overall well-being. These products include dietary supplements, functional foods, herbal extracts, and probiotics, each targeting specific physiological functions. The growing interest in nutraceuticals is driven by increased consumer awareness, lifestyle-related disorders, and the demand for natural alternatives to conventional medicines. Recent advancements in biotechnology and formulation technologies have enhanced the efficacy, bioavailability, and safety of these products. This review explores the classification, mechanisms of action, therapeutic potential, and emerging trends in nutraceutical development, emphasizing their role in preventive healthcare and personalized nutrition.

KEYWORDS: Nutraceuticals, regulatory aspects and challenges, AI Integration, evaluation, molecular docking,

market, adverse effects.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Àharasambhavam vastu rogascaharasambhavah,

Hitahitavisesasca visesah sukhaduhkhayoh

“The physical body is the product of diet and sensory inputs. Similarly, all ailments are the product of faulty dietetics and lifestyle. Wholesome and unwholesome diets and lifestyles are fundamentals of health and disease.” This statement on food reflects the critical importance of food and lifestyle on one’s health.^[1]

Nutraceuticals are known as bioactive substances that are present in common food or botanical-based sources that can be delivered in the form of dietary supplements or functional food, supplying beneficial effects in addition to the nutritional essential components.^[2] Nutraceuticals comprise a wide range of bioactive derivatives accumulated in edible sources including antioxidants, phytochemicals, fatty acids, amino acids, and probiotics. With either established previously or potential effects, nutraceuticals are well-known for their role of being involved in disease treatment and prevention, anti-aging properties, and malignancy prevention. Consuming probiotics is encouraged due to its significant role in the treatment and prevention of gastroenterological diseases.^[3] Garlic, for example, has been suggested as a complementary therapy for high blood pressure and cholesterol.^[4] The “nutraceuticals” combine two words nutrient, which is a nourishing food component and pharmaceutical, which is medical drug. The term nutraceutical was coined in 1989 by Stephen De Felice founder and chairman of the Foundation for Innovation in Medicine, an American organization which encourages medical health research. He defined a nutraceutical as a – food, or parts of a food, that provide medical or health benefits, including the prevention and treatment of disease.^[5] In recent years, however, the food composition has been scientifically tested and verified as people are becoming more and more aware of health-related issues and how food can directly or indirectly be responsible for maintaining proper health and preventing diseases (Figure 1).^[6]

Figure 1.

2.0 History

Nutraceuticals, a type of food substance that helps to maintain health and prevent illness. The term nutraceuticals were introduced in 1989 by American medical doctor Stephen L. De Felice. He concept of Nutraceuticals went back as far as 3000 years ago. Hippocrates(460–377 B.C) stated let food be thy medicine and medicine be thy food'. In the early 1900s the United States of America food manufacturers started adding small quantities of iodine to salt to prevent goiter. The term nutraceuticals were coined in 1989 by Stephen De Felice who was the Chairman and Founder of the Foundation for Innovation in Medicine, Cranford, New Jersey. According to De Felice, nutraceutical can be said to be —a food (or part of a food) that provides medical or health benefits, including the prevention and/or treatment of a disease. However, the term nutraceutical as commonly used in marketing has no regulatory definition. In England, Japan and other countries, nutraceuticals are already becoming part of the dietary landscape. Diet was first considered by Germany, France and the United Kingdom as a more important factor than exercise or hereditary factors in achieving good health. Canada defined them as products of foods but sold in pills, powders, (potions) and other medicinal forms not normally associated with food'. In India, nutraceuticals are seen as the food components made from herbal or botanical raw materials, which are used for preventing or treating different types of chronic and acute maladies. Nowadays, nutraceuticals are one of the most rapidly growing segments of the industry with an expected compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 7.5% (Healthcare Packaging). The global nutraceutical market is estimated to increase from \$241 billion market in 2019 to \$373 billion in 2025 (Healthcare Packaging). The definite use of nutraceuticals has been to achieve desirable therapeutic outcomes with reduced side effects. Herbal Nutraceuticals are powerful instruments in

sustaining health and act contrary to nutritionally induced acute and chronic diseases by promoting optimal health, longevity and quality of life.^[7]

- **Benefits of nutraceuticals**^[8]

1. Increase the health value of our diet.
2. Help us live longer.
3. Help us to avoid particular medical conditions.
4. Help us to avoid particular medical conditions.
5. Show action on immune system, respiratory system and digestive system.
6. Provide the right amount of nutrition for our body.
7. Prevent the signs of ageing as well as chronic diseases.
8. Increase life expectancy and improve immunity.
9. Improve sleep quality and quantity.

- **Limitations**

1. Variable bioavailability and inconsistent therapeutic effect .
2. High cost compared to conventional medicines.
3. Limited clinical evidence to support efficacy.
4. Risk of adulteration and contamination.
5. Uncertain long –term safety profile.
6. Lack of standardization in composition and purity.

3.0 Classification

Nutraceuticals or functional foods can be classified on the basis of various parameters:

Figure 2.

3.1 Based on Food Bioavailability

Traditional Nutraceuticals

They are natural products with no changes to the food. They contain numerous natural components that convey benefits beyond basic nutrition, like omega-3 fatty acids in salmon, saponins in soy or lycopene in tomatoes

1. Chemical Constituents.
2. Nutrients
3. Herbals
4. Phytochemicals
5. Nutraceutical Enzymes
6. Chemical Constituents]
7. Probiotic Microorganisms

Nutrient: The nutrients include amino acids, fatty acids, minerals and vitamins with recognized nutritional functions. Most foods contain vitamins that aid in curing diseases like stroke, cataracts, osteoporosis and heart diseases. Minerals found in plants, animals and dairy products are useful in osteoporosis, anemia and in building strong bones, teeth, muscles, and improving nerve impulses and heart rhythm. Foods that contain fatty acids like omega-3 PUFAs are potent regulators of the inflammatory processes, maintenance of brain function and reduction in cholesterol deposition.

Herbals: Herbal nutraceuticals improve health and help prevent chronic diseases. They show analgesic, anti-inflammatory, astringent, antipyretic, and antiarthritic effects. Flavonoids like apiol and psoralen act as diuretics, carminatives, and antipyretics. Peppermint (*Mentha piperita*) with menthol relieves cold and flu. Tannins aid in managing depression, stress, cough, hypertension, and asthma, while proanthocyanidins help prevent or treat cancer, ulcers, and urinary tract infections.

Phytochemicals: Phytochemicals are plant nutrients with particular biological activities that promote human health. They are also referred to as Phytonutrients. They work by serving as substrate for biochemical reactions, cofactors or inhibitors of enzymatic reactions, absorbents that bind to and eradicate unwanted constituents in the intestine and improve the absorption and/or stability of indispensable nutrients among others.

Nutraceutical Enzymes: These are enzymes that are derived from plant, animal and microbial sources. Enzymes are an essential part of life, without which our bodies would cease to function optimally. Medical conditions such as blood sugar disorders, digestive problems and obesity have their symptoms eliminated by enzyme supplements in the diet.^[9]

Probiotics: Probiotics are microbes that are beneficial to health and used in food, especially in milk products, which are important to promote health by providing immunologic and digestive properties. In addition, these live microbes can improve microbial intestinal balance. *Lactobacillus* with its different species is the most common probiotic used that will survive in the human gut. Currently, *Bifidobacterium* spp., and *Streptococcus* are also used as probiotic strains.^[10]

Prebiotics: Prebiotics are ingredients consisting of short chain carbohydrates that improve the probiotics' activity.^[11] These prebiotics are literally fertilizing agents for probiotics that are not affected by gastric pH and stomach acids. Prebiotics are non-digestible ingredients that promote the growth of productive microorganism and affect the composition and activity of gut microbiota. Fructo-oligosaccharides and inulin are examples of prebiotics used in functional foods to improve gastric health.^[12]

Non-Traditional Nutraceuticals

These are the artificial foods developed by biotechnology. The bioactive components in food samples are engineered to produce products for human wellness. They can be grouped into fortified nutraceuticals and recombinant nutraceuticals.

Fortified Nutraceuticals: Made by adding nutrients/ingredients, e.g., vitamin/mineral cereals, vitamin D milk, folic acid products, probiotic milk (*B. lactis* HN019), and calcium-fortified juice.

Recombinant Nutraceuticals: Produced via fermentation/genetic engineering, including probiotics and bioactive compounds. Examples: biotech foods (bread, yogurt, cheese) and cows engineered with recombinant human lactoferrin to address deficiency.

3.2 Classification based on mechanism of action

1. Anti-inflammatory activity

Nutraceuticals exert anti-inflammatory activities which help in the prevention and treatment of chronic inflammation-associated diseases. Another benefit of nutraceuticals as anti-inflammatory agents is that they can be used as a complementary alternative to anti-inflammatory therapeutic drugs, which leads to a reduction in drug dosage, and therefore reducing side effects. Chronic inflammation is the major cause of chronic diseases such as cardiovascular diseases, pulmonary diseases, diabetes, and cancer.^[13]

2. Anti-cancer activity

The use of nutraceuticals as chemo-preventative agents has been studied, and promising results were obtained as per their ability to prevent and treat cancer. Nutraceuticals of different origins have been shown to exhibit anti-cancer activity. Plants such as garlic, ginseng, curcumin, ginger, and green tea extract express several mechanisms of action against oncogenesis. Such mechanisms include the inhibition of DNA alkylation, tumor initiation, proliferation, and metastasis, in addition to the promotion of autophagy and intrinsic apoptosis.^[14] Furthermore, nutraceuticals have been found to attenuate cancer signaling pathways that are believed to play a role in carcinogenesis. Many studies have been conducted to evaluate nutraceuticals' modes of action against various types of cancer, and a wide range of nutraceuticals have been found to express anti-cancer properties against oral cancer, prostate cancer, breast cancer, lung cancer and colon cancer cells.^[15]

3. Antioxidant activity

The main sources of antioxidants are food, vitamins, and supplements. Foods such as fruits and vegetables are considered a great source of antioxidants due to their high levels of vitamins and phytochemicals.^[16] Beetroot contains betalain and phenolic compounds which cause an increase in the resistance of low-density lipoproteins (LDLs) to oxidation, protect the liver from damage, and decrease blood pressure. Dried fruits are a good source of antioxidants and have health benefits to humans. They can reduce glucose levels in the blood in addition to reducing risk factors associated with heart disease.^[17]

4. Anti-hypercholesteremic activity

Nutraceuticals such as vitamins, minerals, and antioxidants are considered useful in the management of hypercholesterolemia in many conditions such as hypertension, diabetes, and cardiovascular disease.^[18] Hypercholesterolemia is a term used to describe the presence of excessive low-density lipoproteins in blood. The effects of nutraceuticals on lowering lipid profiles in hypercholesteremic patients have been investigated; therefore, this section will discuss nutraceuticals' activity on multiple conditions associated with elevated lipid levels. The application of nutraceuticals as hypolipidemic agents has shown great potential in lowering total cholesterol (TC) and low-density lipoprotein (LDL) concentrations. Lipid-lowering nutraceuticals can be classified into three groups based on their mechanism of action. Such mechanisms include the inhibition of cholesterol absorption, inhibition of cholesterol synthesis, and excretion of LDL.

5. Antihypertensive activity

Nutraceuticals from natural foods aid in hypertension management by inhibiting ACE, promoting vasodilation via nitric oxide, reducing inflammation, and improving glucose/lipid metabolism. Nutrigenetics further enables personalized nutraceutical-based therapy.

3.3 Classification Based On Chemical Nature

1. Isoprenoid derivatives

Isoprenoids, the largest class of phytonutrients in green foods and grains, are vital for photosynthesis in plants and serve hormonal, growth-regulatory, and protective roles in animals (e.g., vitamin A). They help prevent diseases linked to chronic damage. Terpenes, particularly tocotrienols and tocopherols, act as antioxidants by interacting with free radicals in fatty membranes.

2. Carbohydrates

Carbohydrates are essential in the diet, with complex sources like whole grains, fruits, vegetables, and legumes being healthiest due to stable blood glucose effects. Simple carbs are acceptable in small amounts, but processed foods like white bread and sodas raise glucose sharply. Adults should get 45–65% of daily intake (200–300 g) from carbs, providing 4 kcal/g. About 30 g of fiber daily is recommended to lower risks of heart disease, stroke, and digestive problems.^[19]

3. Minerals

Minerals are essential nutrients for growth and metabolism, found naturally in foods and the environment. Classified as macro- or micronutrients, they act as enzyme cofactors, reaction substrates, nutrient absorbers, and regulators of beneficial and harmful bacteria, playing a crucial role in overall human health.^[20]

4. Microbes

Bacteria, yeast, and microalgae are used to produce enzymes, nutraceuticals, flavors, colors, and other metabolites on a large scale. Lactic acid bacteria, especially *Lactococcus lactis*, are effective bio-factories. Microbes also provide terpenes and can aid as adjuvant therapy for conditions like malnutrition, anemia, diarrhea, cancer, obesity, and digestive disorders.^[21]

5. Fatty acids

Omega-3 fatty acids, including ALA, EPA, and DHA, are found in foods and supplements. ALA is in plant oils (flaxseed, soybean, canola) and is essential, while EPA and DHA are in fish and seafood. The body converts ALA to EPA and DHA only minimally, so consuming EPA and DHA directly is the main way to boost levels. Omega-3s are also added to some fortified foods. You can get adequate amounts of omega-3s by eating a variety of foods, including the following:

- Fish and other seafood (especially cold-water fatty fish, such as salmon, mackerel, tuna, herring, and sardines)
- Nuts and seeds (such as flaxseed, chia seeds, and walnuts)
- Plant oils (such as flaxseed oil, soybean oil, and canola oil)
- Fortified foods (such as certain brands of eggs, yogurt, juices, milk, soy beverages, and infant formulas)

What kinds of omega-3 dietary supplements are available?

Omega-3 dietary supplements include fish oil, krill oil, cod liver oil, and algal oil (a vegetarian source that comes from algae). They provide a wide range of doses and forms of omega-3s.

6. Phenolic compounds

Phenolic compounds (PCs) are plant secondary metabolites that protect against UV and pathogens and are major dietary antioxidants. Found in fruits, vegetables, cereals, chocolate, tea, coffee, and red wine, average intake is ~1 g/day—much higher than vitamins C, E, and carotenoids. PCs, often conjugated to sugars or acids, are classified as flavonoids or non-flavonoids based on phenol rings and structure, though classification remains debated.^[22]

4.0 Therapeutic Uses of Nutraceuticals^[23]

Nutraceuticals in Allergic Disorders

Allergies result from immune hypersensitivity, ranging from mild to life-threatening reactions. Quercetin (plant-derived flavonoid) and eucalyptus oil are common nutraceuticals used for allergy management due to their anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties.

Nutraceuticals in Cardiovascular Disease (CVDs)

CVDs are leading global killers but are largely preventable. Nutraceuticals like flavonoids, omega-3 fatty acids, antioxidants, fibers, melatonin, and tannins help reduce risk by lowering cholesterol, preventing platelet aggregation, and improving vascular health. Omega-3s are especially effective in managing arrhythmias and lipid levels.

Nutraceuticals in Diabetes

Diabetes, especially type 2, is linked to obesity and lifestyle. Nutraceuticals such as isoflavones, omega-3 fatty acids, lipoic acid, psyllium, and medicinal plants help control blood glucose, reduce complications, and serve as safer adjuncts to conventional therapies.

Nutraceuticals in Alzheimer's Disease

Alzheimer's is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder with no cure. Nutraceuticals like β -carotene, lycopene, curcumin, lutein, and plant extracts (*Lavandula officinalis*, *Zizyphus jujube*) show promise in memory support and slowing disease progression.

Nutraceuticals in Ophthalmic Disorders

Age-related Macular Degeneration and vision loss can be delayed with antioxidants such as lutein, zeaxanthin, omega-3s, and polyphenols. Carotenoids like astaxanthin (from marine sources) and lutein (from vegetables and fruits) are widely used for eye health.

5.0 Formulation challenges involved

The development of a quality nutraceutical formulation that is physically and chemically stable, safe, technologically feasible, and cost-effective involves several challenges. Unlike drug molecules, which are well-defined chemical entities, botanicals are complex mixtures containing multiple constituents, often representing different classes of compounds within a single product. These botanicals are highly sensitive to environmental factors such as heat, light, oxygen, alkaline pH, and high humidity. Additionally, they often exhibit poor flow properties, low bulk density, and variable particle size distribution.

Hence, the successful development of nutraceutical formulations demands a thorough understanding of the physicochemical properties of diverse ingredients, the application of appropriate manufacturing techniques, careful excipient selection, and the incorporation of suitable manufacturing overages guided by critical stability studies.^[24]

The key areas of emphasis include:

- Challenges across different dosage forms
- Approaches to address formulation challenges
- Selection of suitable excipients.

▪ *Challenges in the Formulation of Nutraceuticals and Dietary Supplement*

Formulating nutraceuticals presents several challenges due to poor aqueous solubility, high melting points, and chemical instability of active constituents. Compounds such as omega-3 fatty acids, carotenoids, oil-soluble vitamins, and curcumin, though nutritionally valuable, exhibit poor solubility. A common approach is to incorporate these into novel delivery systems, but such technologies significantly increase the cost of the final product, highlighting the need for cost-effective alternatives.^[25]

High melting points also complicate formulation. Ingredients like phytosterols, fatty alcohols, and carotenoids tend to destabilize formulations. Solid dispersions or suspensions of nanocrystals in suitable solvents are often employed as solutions. However, these approaches

can reduce stability and shelf life while negatively impacting product appearance, odor, and mouthfeel, thereby affecting consumer acceptance and market value. Hence, more economical technologies must be developed.

Chemical instability further adds to the complexity. Oils rich in omega-3 fatty acids (e.g., fish oil, flaxseed oil, cod liver oil), as well as carotenoids, lycopene, and curcumin, are highly prone to degradation. The rate of chemical breakdown depends on factors such as product composition, environmental conditions (temperature, pH, and pressure), and the presence of oxidation-promoting agents like metals. Nanoscale formulations are often required to improve protection against degradation.

In probiotic formulations, the careful selection of appropriate and safe bacterial strains is critical. The use of mismatched or toxic strains, combined with poor handling, can lead to harmful consequences. Furthermore, although nutraceuticals and pharmaceuticals share similarities in solid dosage formulation and process design, their intended purpose and regulatory requirements differ, adding another layer of complexity. Finally, the development of nutraceutical and dietary supplement dosage forms must account for the needs of specific populations, particularly older adults and children, who may face difficulty swallowing conventional tablets or capsules (dysphagia). In such cases, advanced dosage forms like orodispersible tablets, fast-dissolving films, and easy-to-swallow gels—commonly used in pharmaceuticals—should be considered for nutraceutical applications as well.

Approaches to Deal with Formulation Challenges^[26]

One of the most widely used approaches is isolation or preparation of concentrates of nutraceuticals from natural sources. It is advantageous as most of herbal nutraceuticals are to be administered in a large dose per daily serving. Further, multiple “active ingredients” are present in different sources. There is significant variation in active ingredient composition and flow characteristics within one dosage form. There are large variations in heat and moisture sensitivity of ingredients within one formula. Significant stability challenges are there with multiple opportunities for interaction. Different extraction processes involve microwave-assisted extraction, counter current extraction, maceration, percolation and Soxhlet extraction. Natural bioactive compounds are plant extracts; herbal concentrates; fruit, vegetable and specialty concentrates; and fungal and microbial materials, which are included in feedstock to produce concentrates (bio-fermentation process). Concentrates may include excipients used in production (such as spray dried carriers).^[27] Novel Drug Delivery Systems,

like nanoformulations, are used to enhance supplement properties. For example, polyphenols from foods have low bioavailability due to poor absorption. Techniques like nanoformulations, enzymatic treatment, and probiotics can overcome this challenge.

Liposomes and Nanoemulsions

Liposomes (bilayer phospholipid vesicles) can encapsulate both hydrophilic and lipophilic compounds, improving protection, bioavailability, sustained release, and stability of sensitive bioactives. Lipid-based nanocarriers like nanophytosomes are used for delivering botanical nutraceuticals in functional foods and beverages. For example, rutin–phosphatidylcholine (1:3) phytosome complexes (<100 nm, 99% efficiency) enhanced rutin's stability and masked its undesirable properties.

Lipid-Based Carriers

Lipid formulations in the form of nanocapsules, micronized carries are potential candidates to be used to effectively enhance the controlled release, solubility and bioavailability of phenolic compounds. As an example, β -Car nanocapsules (>300 nm), due to their physical stability showed only negligible variations during storage, which suggested that they can be widely used as functional foods and beverages along with being nutraceutical products.

Polysaccharide Matrices

These are the kind of matrices that have numerous enzymatic exposures that guarantee degradation at specific points in the large and small intestine. When being used as a nanoparticle coating, they can effectively retard the nonspecific release of bioactive components encapsulated within until the coating is exposed in the intended environment where it was intended to be released. These coated nanoparticles can potentially be used to target various diverse organs of the GI tract to help improve the oral bioavailability.

Excipient Selection

Formulation challenges in nutraceuticals can be addressed by selecting suitable excipients. The final product must be robust enough to handle variations in natural ingredient properties. Excipient performance depends on the specific formulation and manufacturing process, as an excipient effective in one formula may fail in another. In natural product formulations, the interaction of multiple actives often affects excipient functionality, and seemingly similar excipients may perform differently.

6.0 Delivery approaches for Nutraceuticals^[21]

The growing global nutraceutical market has brought attention to their delivery challenges, as many bioactive compounds (e.g., silymarin, curcumin, lycopene, ascorbic acid, alpha-tocopherol) suffer from poor absorption, degradation in the GIT, and first-pass metabolism, limiting efficacy.

To overcome these issues, modern drug delivery approaches—especially nanotechnology-based systems such as nanoparticles, nanoemulsions, micelles, liposomes, phytosomes, and nano-suspensions—are widely explored. These systems improve bioavailability, stability, absorption, and targeted delivery, while also reducing toxicity. Advanced technologies like Nano-Sized Self-Assembled Structured Liquid (NSSL) further protect nutraceuticals in the GIT and enhance delivery efficiency. However, cost remains a critical factor affecting consumer acceptance. Despite some products being under clinical trials and facing market challenges, nutraceuticals show promise in managing chronic and degenerative diseases (e.g., cancer, diabetes, Alzheimer's, Parkinson's). With ongoing innovations, nutraceuticals are expected to play a leading role in healthcare in the coming years.

S.N	Delivery Approaches	Nutraceutical	Intended Effect
1	Nano complex	Beta-carotene, folic acid, curcumin and ergocalciferol	Nutraceutical delivery
2	Phytosomes	Silymarin	Oral delivery
3	Nutraceutical conjugated Gold nanoparticle	Querecetin ,Andrograph olide	Leishmaniasis
4	Nanospheres & Nanocapsules	Curcumin	Oral delivery
5	Metal nanoparticles	Garlic,cayenne pepper	Antibacterial activity
6	Colloidal nanoparticles	Curcumin	Anticancer oral delivery
7	Nano hydrogel	Curcumin, caffeine	Oral delivery
8	Liposome delivery	Ginseng extract , Curcumin	Oral delivery
9	Solid lipid nanoparrticles	Alpha –lipoic acid	Topical delivery
10	Nanostructure lipid carriers	Resveratrol	Oral delivery
11	Dendrimers	Green tea extract, ginseng	Oral delivery, nasal delivery
12	Biopolymer nanoparticles	Casein, zein, zein - Querecetin	Oral delivery
13	Nanosuspensions	Curcumin	Oral delivery
14	Nano-complexes	Beta lactoglobulin	Oral delivery
15	Gold nanoparticles	Querecetin	Antileishmanial efficiency

7.0 Significance of Bioavailability in Nutraceuticals^[28-36]

Pharmacokinetics (PK) and Bioavailability (BA) in Nutraceuticals

PK studies, essential in drug development, are often lacking in Ayurvedic, herbal, and nutraceutical products due to non-standardized, low-concentration, or unidentified active compounds. This complicates ADME (absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion) profiling and raises concerns about herb–drug interactions, especially with cytochrome P450 enzymes.

Bioavailability (BA) in nutraceuticals refers to the fraction of a bioactive compound that is absorbed, metabolized, and reaches target tissues. Unlike pharmaceuticals, nutraceutical BA considers release from the food matrix, GI absorption, metabolism, and distribution. BA and clearance are critical for maintaining steady-state concentrations, while route of administration and dosage strongly affect outcomes (e.g., oral formulations face first-pass metabolism).

BA is influenced by bioaccessibility, absorption, metabolism, and bioactivity, studied through *in vivo*, *ex vivo*, and *in vitro* models. The Nutraceutical Bioavailability Classification Scheme (NuBACS) categorizes BA limitations into:

1. Bioaccessibility
2. Absorption
3. Transformation in GIT

Examples

Quercetin, resveratrol → limited by poor solubility & high metabolism

β-carotene, curcumin → limited by low absorption & instability

Improved delivery systems and food matrices can enhance nutraceutical bioavailability and therapeutic efficacy.

8.0 Adverse effects of nutraceuticals^[37]

1. Vitamins and minerals

Vitamin B6 (Pyridoxine)

- ✓ Photosensitivity
- ✓ Neurotoxicity at doses >500 mg/day
- ✓ Chronic sensory polyneuropathy in elderly multivitamin users

Vitamin E (α -tocopherol)

- ✓ Bleeding due to antiplatelet action (800–1200 mg/day)
- ✓ Diarrhea, weakness, blurred vision, gonadal dysfunction (>1200 mg/day)
- ✓ Increased cancer recurrence after radiation therapy (head & neck cancer patients)
- ✓ Increased all-cause mortality at high doses (meta-analysis)

Vitamin A & β -carotene

- ✓ Increased risk of lung cancer in male smokers (β -carotene supplements)
- ✓ Increased prostate cancer incidence and mortality in alcohol users (β -carotene)
- ✓ Bone-related issues: low bone mineral density, higher fracture risk (excess vitamin A)
- ✓ Congenital abnormalities in women consuming high doses during pregnancy
- ✓ Intra-hepatic cholestasis (chronic hypervitaminosis A, long-term use)

Minerals (Iron)

- ✓ Hyperchromatosis (iron storage disease) → liver injury
- ✓ Risk worsened with alcohol consumption.

2. Omega -3 Fatty acids and Fish Oil

- ✓ Hypervitaminosis A
- ✓ May occur when fish liver oils (rich in vitamin A) are consumed along with multivitamin supplements.
- ✓ Increased Bleeding Risk
- ✓ Omega-3 fatty acids and fish oils can exacerbate anticoagulation and promote bleeding, particularly in patients on anticoagulant therapy (e.g., warfarin).

3. Weight loss, Sports & Bodybuilding Supplements

- ✓ Weight-loss supplements → psychiatric, cardiovascular, GI, and liver toxicities (notably ephedra, DMAA, aegeline).
- ✓ Sports supplements → cardiovascular risks (DMAA, stimulants) and liver injury (multi-ingredient mixes).
- ✓ Bodybuilding supplements → hepatotoxicity, hormonal disturbances, cardiomyopathy, and steroid-related adverse effects.

4. Adverse effects of commonly used nutraceuticals

- ✓ Green tea extract(EGCG): Risk of oxidative stress & liver toxicity.

- ✓ Soy isoflavones (genistein, daidzein, equol): Hormonal effects → fertility issues, reproductive malformations, tumor stimulation.
- ✓ Isoflavone supplements: Risk of endometriosis & estrogen-sensitive cancers.

Molecular docking validations of nutraceuticals targets in diseases

Theory of molecular docking validation of nutraceuticals. Molecular docking validation is a com-

9.0 Molecular Docking validation of nutraceuticals target in diseases^[38]

○ Theory of molecular docking validation of nutraceuticals

Molecular docking validation is a computational approach that is increasingly being used in the field of nutraceutical research to identify potential targets for the management of various diseases. Nutraceuticals are naturally occurring compounds that have potential health benefits and are found in food sources such as fruits, vegetables, and herbs. With the rise of chronic diseases such as diabetes, cardiovascular disease, and cancer, there is a growing interest in the use of nutraceuticals as a complementary approach to conventional medical treatments. Molecular docking validation can help researchers identify potential nutraceutical targets for disease management, providing a more efficient and cost-effective way to screen potential treatments before proceeding with costly clinical trials. This method makes drug discovery more ethical since it lessens the need for animal testing throughout the development of novel medicines. Molecular docking discovery of nutraceuticals targets. Molecular docking is a computational technique used to predict the interactions between small molecules, such as nutraceuticals, and larger biomolecules, such as enzymes, receptors, RNA, DNA, and other proteins. The technique involves the simulation of the molecular interactions between the small molecule and the target biomolecule, which can provide insights into the binding affinity, binding site, and possible mechanism of action.

Enzymes-Enzymes are proteins that catalyze chemical reactions in the body. Nutraceuticals such as curcumin, resveratrol, quercetin, hesperidin, etc., have been shown to interact with enzymes and modulate their activity. For example, curcumin has been shown to inhibit the activity of the enzyme COX-2, which is involved in the inflammatory response. Molecular docking can predict the binding site and the strength of the interaction between the nutraceutical and the enzyme, which can help in understanding the mechanism of action and the potential therapeutic benefits.

Receptors-Receptors are proteins that bind to specific molecules, such as hormones, neurotransmitters, and drugs, and initiate a cellular response. Nutraceuticals can also interact with receptors and modulate their activity. For example, resveratrol was able to activate the sirtuin family of proteins, which are involved in cellular metabolism and aging. Molecular docking can predict the binding site and the strength of the interaction between the nutraceutical and the receptor, which can help in understanding the mechanism of action and the potential therapeutic benefits.

RNA and DNA-. Nucleic acids such as RNA and DNA are essential for the storage and transfer of genetic information. By attaching to their structures or changing their expression, nutraceuticals can also interact with RNA or DNA and affect their function. For instance, it has been demonstrated that the enzyme topoisomerase, which is involved in DNA replication and repair, is inhibited by quercetin. According to Singh *et al.*, molecular docking can forecast how nutraceuticals may interact with DNA and RNA sequences like telomerase reverse transcriptase (TERT) and microRNAs (miRNAs). Furthermore, molecular docking can forecast the binding location and intensity of the interaction between the nutraceutical and RNA or DNA, which aids in understanding the mechanism of action.

Epigenetic markers- According to recent studies [21,22], epigenetic changes, which can change gene expression without affecting the underlying DNA sequence, are significant targets for nutraceuticals. Molecular docking can predict how nutraceuticals may interact with proteins involved in epigenetic regulation, such as histone deacetylases (HDACs), DNA methyltransferases (DNMTs), and transcription factors/nuclear receptors like estrogen receptors, androgen receptors, fibroblast growth factors [21,23]. These epigenetic modifications can lead to transgenerational effects.

Other proteins- Nutraceuticals may potentially target other proteins in the body, including transporters, ion channels, and structural proteins. Hesperidin, for instance, has been demonstrated to block the activity of alpha-glucosidase, an enzyme involved in the breakdown of carbohydrates. To understand the mechanism of action and possible therapeutic effects, molecular docking can predict the binding site and the degree of interaction between the nutraceutical and the protein target.

10.0 Artificial Intelligence in Nutraceuticals^[39]

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is poised to bring about transformative changes in various industries, and nutraceutical research and development (R&D) are no exception. The integration of AI technologies holds the potential to revolutionize how new nutraceutical products are discovered, developed, and brought to market. Here's a closer look at the ways AI is expected to reshape the landscape of nutraceutical R&D:

1. Accelerated Discovery and Formulation

AI algorithms can analyze vast datasets, including information on nutrients, compounds, and their effects on the human body. This accelerates the discovery of novel combinations and formulations, enabling researchers to identify potential nutraceutical candidates more efficiently.

2. Personalized Nutrition Solutions

AI's ability to process individual health data, genetic information, and lifestyle factors facilitates the development of personalized nutraceutical solutions. Tailoring products to specific genetic profiles and health needs enhances their efficacy and resonates with the growing demand for personalized nutrition.

3. Predictive Analytics for Health Outcomes

AI-driven predictive analytics can assess the potential health outcomes of nutraceutical interventions. By analyzing data from clinical trials, real-world evidence, and individual health records, AI can provide insights into the long-term impact of nutraceuticals on diverse populations.

4. Drug-Nutrient Interaction Analysis

AI algorithms can analyze complex interactions between nutraceuticals and pharmaceuticals. This is crucial for identifying potential synergies or conflicts between dietary supplements and medications, ensuring the safety and efficacy of combined regimens.

5. Virtual Screening and Drug Design

AI facilitates virtual screening of potential nutraceutical compounds and aids in the design of novel molecules. This computational approach streamlines the early stages of R&D, allowing researchers to focus resources on the most promising candidates.

6. Optimization of Nutrient Delivery Systems

AI algorithms can optimize the formulation and delivery systems of nutraceuticals. This includes designing efficient delivery mechanisms that enhance bioavailability, absorption, and overall effectiveness of the nutrients.

7. Data-Driven Clinical Trials

AI can design and optimize clinical trial protocols by analyzing historical trial data, identifying relevant patient populations, and predicting potential trial outcomes. This data-driven approach improves the efficiency and success rates of nutraceutical clinical trials.

8. Market Trend Analysis and Consumer Insights

AI tools can analyze market trends, consumer preferences, and social media sentiments to provide valuable insights for product development. This data-driven approach helps nutraceutical companies align their products with consumer demands.

9. Regulatory Compliance and Documentation

AI can assist in navigating complex regulatory landscapes by automating compliance processes and ensuring adherence to industry standards. This streamlines the regulatory approval process for new nutraceutical products.

10. Continuous Learning and Adaptation

AI enables nutraceutical R&D to continuously learn from new data and research, keeping products innovative and aligned with the latest scientific advancements. Its integration promises greater efficiency, personalization, and a transformative shift in how nutraceuticals are developed and delivered, benefiting both consumers and the field of nutritional science.

Transforming Nutraceutical Production: The Impact of AI

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is reshaping nutraceutical production by driving efficiency, innovation, and sustainability. Key applications include:

1. **Automated Quality Control** – AI-based image recognition ensures defect-free products and consistent quality.
2. **Predictive Maintenance** – Real-time equipment monitoring reduces downtime and boosts efficiency.
3. **Process Optimization** – Data-driven insights minimize waste and enhance performance.
4. **Supply Chain Management** – AI predicts demand, prevents disruptions, and streamlines inventory.
5. **Customize Batch Production** – Flexible batch manufacturing enables personalized nutraceuticals.
6. **Energy Efficiency** – Smart algorithms cut electricity, water, and raw material use.
7. **Continuous Monitoring & Feedback** – Real-time adjustments maintain optimal production conditions.
8. **Waste Reduction** – Ingredient optimization reduces losses and improves sustainability.
9. **Regulatory Compliance** – Automated documentation ensures adherence to safety standards.
10. **Enhanced Product Innovation** – Consumer trend analysis drives the creation of new formulations.

Revolutionizing Nutraceutical Analysis: The Impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI)

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into nutraceutical analysis is set to transform nutrition and wellness by enhancing precision, efficiency, and personalization.

1. **Data Integration:** AI processes vast datasets from trials, genomics, literature, and consumer trends, enabling deeper insights into nutraceutical impacts.
2. **Predictive Modeling:** AI forecasts efficacy based on molecular structure, bioavailability, and genetics, guiding smarter study designs.
3. **Personalized Nutrition:** By analyzing health data and lifestyle factors, AI tailors nutraceutical recommendations to individual needs.
4. **Biomarker Monitoring:** AI identifies and tracks biomarkers, offering real-time feedback on intervention effectiveness.

5. **Interaction Prediction:** AI anticipates drug-nutrient interactions, ensuring safe and complementary regimens.
6. **Faster Formulation:** AI predicts optimal ingredient combinations, synergies, and dosages, speeding up product development.
7. **Automated Reviews:** AI tools scan literature efficiently, keeping researchers updated on the latest findings. AI is thus revolutionizing nutraceutical analysis by making it smarter, faster, and more personalized.
8. **Quality Control in Production:** AI systems can enhance quality control in nutraceutical production. By analyzing data from various stages of manufacturing, AI ensures consistency in product composition, adherence to specifications, and compliance with regulatory standards.
9. **Detection of Contaminants and Adulterants:** AI technologies can detect contaminants and adulterants in nutraceutical products. Through advanced image recognition and spectral analysis, AI ensures the purity and safety of products, safeguarding consumer health.
10. **Real-Time Monitoring of Clinical Trials:** AI enables real-time monitoring and analysis of clinical trial data. This ensures the timely identification of trends, potential side effects, and overall trial progress, expediting the research and development lifecycle.

In conclusion, the integration of AI in nutraceutical analysis represents a paradigm shift in the industry. By leveraging the power of advanced algorithms and data analytics, researchers and practitioners can unlock new dimensions of understanding, efficiency, and personalization in the development and assessment of nutraceutical products. This synergy between AI and nutraceutical analysis holds the potential to revolutionize the field, offering unprecedented insights for improving human health and well-being.

Revolutionizing Nutraceutical Marketing and Distribution: The Impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is redefining marketing and distribution across industries, with nutraceuticals being no exception. By enhancing personalization, streamlining operations, and improving decision-making, AI unlocks new opportunities for growth in this sector.

1. **Personalized Campaigns:** AI analyzes consumer data—preferences, demographics, purchase history—to craft tailored campaigns, boosting engagement and conversions.

2. **Predictive Analytics:** AI anticipates consumer trends, enabling companies to forecast demand, refine strategies, and launch timely products.
3. **Chatbots & Assistants:** AI-driven tools provide instant, personalized responses, product guidance, and purchasing support, enhancing customer satisfaction.
4. **Influencer Strategy:** AI identifies the right influencers by analyzing engagement data, ensuring collaborations reach the right audiences.
5. **Dynamic Pricing:** Real-time adjustments based on demand, competitor activity, and consumer behavior keep pricing competitive.
6. **Targeted Ads:** AI pinpoints audience segments with precision, making ad campaigns more effective and cost-efficient.
7. **Supply Chain Optimization:** With full supply chain visibility, AI supports better inventory, fulfillment, and logistics management.
8. **Retention Strategies:** AI predicts churn and helps design loyalty programs and personalized offers to boost customer retention.
9. **E-commerce Personalization:** Online platforms use AI to recommend products, tailor discounts, and create seamless shopping experiences.
10. **Fraud Detection:** AI enhances transaction security by identifying and preventing fraudulent activities in real time.

The Future of India's Nutraceutical Industry: A 10-Year Outlook

India's nutraceutical industry is set for remarkable growth over the next decade, driven by evolving consumer preferences, technological advances, and an increased focus on preventive healthcare.

1. **Rapid Market Growth:** Rising awareness of wellness and higher disposable incomes will fuel strong demand for nutraceuticals.
2. **Broader Product Portfolio:** Expect innovations in formulations, delivery systems, and specialized ingredients to expand product offerings.
3. **Personalized Nutrition:** AI and genetic testing will enable tailored solutions based on individual health profiles and lifestyles.
4. **Functional Ingredients:** Superfoods, adaptogens, and bioactives with proven benefits will gain prominence in formulations.
5. **Digital Health Platforms:** Apps and digital channels will deliver nutrition advice, consumer engagement, and online sales.

6. **Stronger Regulations:** A more robust framework will ensure safety, efficacy, and transparent labeling, boosting consumer trust.
7. **Mainstream Retail Presence:** Wider availability in supermarkets, pharmacies, and e-commerce will expand reach and accessibility.
8. **Sustainability Focus:** Ethical sourcing, eco-friendly packaging, and transparent practices will align with consumer values.
9. **Collaborations & Partnerships:** Increased ties between companies, research bodies, and tech firms will accelerate innovation.
10. **Immune Health Emphasis:** Demand for immune-boosting products will remain strong, supported by ongoing global health priorities.

CONCLUSION

Over the next decade, India's nutraceutical sector will evolve into a dynamic, innovation-driven industry. With personalization, sustainability, and digital engagement at its core, it is poised to play a central role in advancing holistic wellness nationwide.

11.0 Nutraceuticals Market^[40]

Nutraceuticals Market Summary

The global nutraceuticals market was valued at USD 591.1 billion in 2024 and is projected to reach USD 919.1 billion by 2030, growing at a CAGR of 7.6% (2025–2030). Growth is driven by rising awareness of preventive healthcare and the role of diet in well-being.

Key Insights (2024)

Asia Pacific held the largest share (38.9% of revenue).

China is expected to grow fastest (CAGR 8.6%).

Dietary supplements accounted for 32.6% of revenue.

Weight management & satiety applications made up 16.6%.

Offline channels dominated distribution with 79.0% share.

Market Drivers

Aging populations fueling demand for products supporting joint, cognitive, and cardiovascular health. Rising chronic diseases (obesity, diabetes) encouraging adoption of healthier lifestyles and nutraceuticals.

Consumers are increasingly demanding clean-label, plant-based nutraceuticals sourced from fruits, vegetables, herbs, and botanicals. Advances in extraction and processing are enabling more potent, bioavailable formulations, while ethical and sustainable practices further influence purchasing decisions.

Personalized nutrition and gut health are also major growth drivers, with rising demand for probiotics, prebiotics, and tailored supplements supported by advances in diagnostics and health-tracking technologies.

Accessibility via e-commerce and convenient formats like gummies, powders, and drinks are expanding market reach, while endorsements from healthcare professionals and influencers strengthen consumer trust.

Product Insights

Dietary Supplements (32.6% share, 2024): Growth fueled by preventive healthcare trends, aging populations, and personalized nutrition. Demand for probiotics, prebiotics, and advanced delivery systems (e.g., liposomes, nanotech) is reshaping the segment.

Functional Beverages (7.6% CAGR, 2025–2030): Rising preference for healthier, natural, and convenient alternatives to sugary drinks. Growth driven by fitness culture, sports/performance drinks, innovative flavors, and ingredients like adaptogens and nootropics.

Application Insights

Weight Management & Satiety (16.6% share, 2024): Rising obesity rates drive demand for natural, convenient solutions that promote satiety, metabolism, and gut health. Focus is

shifting from quick fixes to holistic wellness, with ready-to-drink shakes, bars, and powders gaining traction.

Men's Health (13.5% CAGR, 2025–2030): Growth fueled by proactive approaches to vitality, hormonal balance, prostate health, and performance. Declining stigma around men's health, fitness culture, and active lifestyle trends are boosting demand for targeted supplements.

Distribution Channel Insights

- **Offline Sales (79.0% share, 2024):** Pharmacies, supermarkets, and specialty stores dominate due to trust, product variety, and personalized recommendations. While offline presence remains strong, growth is challenged by e-commerce, pushing retailers to enhance in-store experiences and customer engagement.

- **Online Sales (10.6% CAGR, 2025–2030):** Growth driven by convenience, wider product selection, reviews, and competitive pricing. COVID-19 accelerated adoption, while direct-to-consumer brands strengthen customer engagement.

Regional Insights

North America (31.8% share, 2024): Growth supported by preventative healthcare focus, aging populations, and demand for personalized, clean-label, and plant-based products.

U.S. (6.2% CAGR, 2025–2030): High prevalence of chronic diseases fuels demand for supplements, sports nutrition, and weight management products. E-commerce is a key channel.

Europe (6.9% CAGR, 2025–2030): Aging demographics and chronic disease rates drive demand for cardiovascular, joint, and cognitive health products. Consumers prefer natural, organic, and plant-based options.

Germany: Leading market with strong focus on science-backed supplements for immune support, joint pain, and sleep. Growing preference for natural and organic products.

Asia Pacific (9.0% CAGR, 2025–2030): Rising incomes, health awareness, and aging populations support growth. Strong demand for immunity, digestive, and cognitive health products, influenced by both traditional remedies and modern supplements. E-commerce and smart tech adoption fuel expansion, especially among younger consumers.

China (8.6% CAGR, 2025–2030): Growth driven by a rising middle class, health-conscious consumers, and government health initiatives. Traditional Chinese medicine influences demand for immunity, beauty, and children’s health products. E-commerce dominates, with reliance on reviews and influencer marketing, while a complex regulatory environment requires constant adaptation.

Japan: A mature market shaped by an aging population and strong preventive healthcare culture. Demand centers on healthy aging, cognition, and joint mobility, with preference for scientifically proven products. Both retail (pharmacies, specialty stores) and e-commerce remain strong sales channels.

Australia & New Zealand (9.5% CAGR, 2025–2030): Growth fueled by focus on preventive healthcare, natural wellness, and active lifestyles. High demand for digestive health, immune support, and sports nutrition. Consumers favor clean-label, sustainable products aligned with outdoor and fitness-oriented lifestyles.

- **Key Nutraceuticals Companies**

The following are the leading companies in the **nutraceuticals market**. These companies collectively hold the largest market share and dictate industry trends.

- Amway Corp.
- Yakult Honsha Co., Ltd.
- General Mills Inc.
- Danone
- Nestlé S.A.
- The Kraft Heinz Company
- The Hain Celestial Group, Inc.
- Herbalife Nutrition Ltd.
- Tyson Foods
- Haleon Group of companies
- Otsuka Pharmaceutical
- GlaxoSmithKline plc.

IMPACT OF COVID-19^[41]

The COVID-19 pandemic heavily and positively affected the market across the globe. There have been reports of a massive increase in demand for products that claim to enhance health and immunity. The circulation of advice from doctors globally to incorporate functional foods and dietary supplements in daily life to aid the immune system greatly contributes to the high adoption of these types of products.

The industry's growth is primarily driven by increased consumer awareness about the benefits of consumption of health supplements, growing consciousness about preventive healthcare measures, and a rising population of affluent and health-conscious consumers. The rapid spread of COVID-19 globally encourages people to shift toward products that support their immune health and adopt preventive healthcare measures that significantly boost product sales. Since the onset of the pandemic globally, panic buying of dietary supplements, functional foods, and beverages by consumers contributed to the exponential growth in the product's sales in retail distribution channels.

KEY INDUSTRY DEVELOPMENTS^[41]

Jan 2024- Zingavita (India) raised USD 1.2M in pre-series A funding for nutraceuticals and supplements.

May 2023 – Kirin Holdings (Japan) partnered with Kellogg's to launch All-Bran with postbiotics & fermented fiber in Japan to support immune health.

Apr 2023 – Fonterra (NZ) launched functional beverages (Actif-Fiber, Anchor-Beaute) in SE Asia, in collaboration with 7-Eleven.

Feb 2021 – TopGum (Israel) expanded to the U.S. with TopGum Inc. (New Jersey) to scale functional gummy supplements in North America & Europe.

Jan 2021 – Alpine Start (USA) launched With Benefits functional beverages via Kickstarter, fortified with vitamins, minerals, and MCTs.

12.0 Evaluation parameters of Nutraceuticals^[42]

Nutraceuticals are evaluated using the same analytical techniques as pharmaceuticals, such as HPTLC, HPLC, GC, CC, and TLC. Phytochemical analysis helps characterize mono- or polyherbal formulations and may also involve non-chromatographic assays for compound groups like alkaloids, glycosides, etc. HPTLC is commonly used for fingerprinting and quantifying unique, abundantly present markers, while HPLC is employed for the quantification of specific markers requiring higher sensitivity. These chromatographic methods should be validated for specificity, linearity, range, accuracy, precision (including repeatability, intermediate precision, and reproducibility), detection and quantitation limits, robustness, and system suitability testing. To establish acceptable limits for both raw materials and finished products, it is recommended to analyze at least three batches of the final product along with a minimum of two batches each of extracts/herbs and in-process samples.

Impurity Analysis

The selection of tests, the number of batches, and the manufacturing stages included in impurity testing should be determined carefully, considering the product type, potential impurities, results of reverse testing (starting with the finished product), and statistical sampling approaches. Commonly performed impurity analyses include heavy metal testing, pesticide residue analysis, and microbial testing.

13.0 The Future of Nutraceuticals: Emerging Trends and Innovations in Health^[43]

The nutraceuticals industry is progressing rapidly, fueled by technological innovations and changing consumer demands. Artificial intelligence (AI) is playing a pivotal role in optimizing formulations, delivering personalized health solutions, and improving production efficiency. With consumers placing greater emphasis on health and wellness, the demand for dietary supplements and functional foods continues to rise.

Industry growth is expected to accelerate as awareness of nutraceuticals' role in managing chronic diseases and enhancing overall well-being expands. Projections show sustained market expansion, creating significant opportunities for innovation and profitability. Staying informed about these developments ensures a competitive edge, whether as a consumer aiming to improve health or as a business looking to leverage emerging opportunities.

Emerging Trends in Nutraceuticals

The sector is experiencing major shifts due to technological progress and evolving consumer preferences. Notable trends include AI integration, the rise of functional foods, the effects of climate change, and advancements in research and clinical trials.

Personalized Nutrition and AI

AI is revolutionizing nutraceuticals by enabling personalized nutrition strategies. By analyzing genetic, biochemical, and lifestyle data, AI provides tailored dietary recommendations, moving beyond generic approaches. This customization supports more effective health outcomes. Additionally, AI is transforming product development by ensuring formulations align with individual needs, making nutraceuticals increasingly targeted and efficient.

Growing Demand for Functional Foods

Functional foods are becoming more popular as consumers seek products that combine nutrition with health benefits. Enriched with vitamins, minerals, probiotics, and other bioactive compounds, these foods are designed to address specific concerns such as immunity support or gut health. With rising awareness of preventive healthcare, demand for functional foods is expected to increase significantly.

Climate Change and Its Impact

Climate change is reshaping the nutraceuticals industry by influencing the availability and quality of raw materials. Shifts in weather patterns and extreme events affect crop yields and nutrient content, pushing the need for sustainable sourcing practices.

Innovations Driving Nutraceuticals Forward

The nutraceutical industry is evolving rapidly, with innovations reshaping how products are designed, regulated, and consumed. Current advancements emphasize immune health, regulatory adaptation, and sustainable growth, paving the way for a more consumer-focused and resilient market.

Immune Function & Preventive Health

Growing health awareness drives demand for immune-supporting products with probiotics, vitamins, and herbal extracts. Personalized nutrition, enabled by technologies like 3D printing, is shifting the market from standardized to customized supplements, boosting self-care and holistic health trends.

Regulatory Shifts & Consumer Trust

Global regulations (U.S., China, Israel, India) are strengthening safety and quality standards. Technologies like AI and blockchain improve compliance and supply chain transparency, enhancing consumer confidence in nutraceuticals.

Sustainable Growth & Expanding Markets

Eco-friendly packaging and green manufacturing support sustainability. Rising demand in developing regions, strategic partnerships, and R&D investments, along with preference for natural/organic products, are driving inclusive global market expansion.

14.0 Marketed formulations^[44,45]

Product	Category	Contents	Manufacturer
Calcitrol D-3	Calcium supplement	Calcium and Vitamins	Cadila Healthcare Limited, Ahmedabad, India.
GRD	Nutritional supplement	Proteins, vitamins, minerals, carbohydrates	ZydusCadilaLtd, Amedabad, India
Proteinx®	Protein supplement	Predigested proteins, vitamins, minerals, and carbohydrates	Pfizer Ltd., Mumbai, India
Coral calcium	Calcium supplement	Calcium and trace minerals	Nature's Answer, Hauppauge, NY, USA

Chyawanprash	Immunobooster	Aamla, ashwagandha, Pippali	Dabur India, Ltd.
Omegawoman	Immune Supplement	Antioxidants, vitamins, Phytochemicals	Wassen, Surrey, UK
Pediasure	Nutritious supplements, Supports immune system	Antioxidants (vitamins C and E, & Selenium)	Abbott
Horlicks	Nutrition for growth and supplement	Antioxidants, vitamins, minerals and proteins	GlaxosmithKlineconsumer healthcare
Amul	Nutritious supplement	Skimmed milk, sucrose, Carbohydrates, minerals	Gujarat Co-operative Milk Marketing Federation
Nutrifit	Improve body composition, boost your energy	Carbohydrates, proteins, vitamins, lipids and minerals	Mother Dairy Fruit and Vegetables
Yakult	Probiotics, immunity booster	<i>Lactobacillus CaseiShirota</i>	Yakult

15.0 Regulation of Nutraceuticals in India^[7]

In India, nutraceuticals and dietary supplements are categorized as “foods for specific dietary uses.” The Food Safety and Standards Act (FSSA), 2006 provides the legal framework for their regulation. It defines categories such as functional foods, nutraceuticals, and health supplements.

The Act established the Food Safety and Standards Authority of India (FSSAI), which is responsible for regulating the production, storage, distribution, sale, and import of nutraceuticals. This Act replaced earlier legislations like the Prevention of Food Adulteration Act, 1954 and the Vegetable Oil Products Order, 1955.

The FSSAI sets product standards based on scientific principles to ensure the availability of safe and wholesome food for consumers.

Indian Regulatory Process (FSSAI)

The regulation of nutraceuticals in India is overseen by the FSSAI and involves the following key steps:

1. FSSAI License – Mandatory license for manufacturers, distributors, and importers.
2. Product Categorization – Classification of products as nutraceuticals, functional foods, health supplements, or special dietary foods.
3. Labeling Requirements – Clear labeling with nutritional information, dosage, ingredient list, and necessary warnings.

4. Quality and Safety Assurance – Compliance with safety standards and regular quality checks.
5. Commercials and Claims – Only scientifically substantiated health claims are permitted on packaging and advertisements.
6. Inspections and Compliance – Routine inspections and audits to ensure adherence to FSSAI guidelines.

Regulatory Challenges^[7]

Nutraceuticals face a number of regulatory challenges worldwide, as they are often placed in a grey zone between food and pharmaceutical products. Some of the key challenges include:
Lack of Harmonized Regulations.

Regulations for nutraceuticals vary widely across countries, and there is no global harmonization. This makes it difficult for companies to operate internationally and often leads to inconsistencies in product safety and quality.

Safety Concerns

Although many nutraceuticals are generally considered safe, cases of adverse effects and even fatalities have been reported. The absence of strict pre-market safety evaluations and post-market surveillance makes it difficult to ensure consumer safety.

Labeling and Marketing Claims

Nutraceuticals frequently carry health claims on labels and advertisements. However, these claims are often not backed by solid scientific evidence. Regulatory authorities across the globe are becoming stricter about unverified claims, creating challenges for companies in promoting their products.

Quality Control

Since nutraceuticals are primarily derived from natural sources, variations in potency, purity, and stability are common. Ensuring consistent quality standards is difficult, making quality control a major challenge for the industry.

Intellectual Property Issues

Protecting innovations in nutraceuticals through patents and trademarks can be complex. Smaller companies, in particular, face difficulties in competing with established players due to these intellectual property barriers.

Lack of Clinical Trials

While a few nutraceuticals have been studied scientifically, many have not undergone rigorous clinical trials. This raises questions about their efficacy and limits acceptance by healthcare professionals.

16.0 CONCLUSION

Nutraceuticals serve as a vital link between nutrition and medicine, offering therapeutic benefits beyond basic dietary requirements. Their historical background, broad classification, and diverse applications reflect their growing global acceptance in preventing and managing chronic disorders. Despite challenges related to formulation, bioavailability, and regulatory frameworks, advancements in delivery technologies, molecular docking, and AI-driven innovations are steadily enhancing their potential. With a rapidly expanding market and rising health awareness, nutraceuticals are emerging as future-oriented solutions for wellness. Ensuring robust evaluation standards and strong regulatory policies, particularly in India, will be essential to guarantee safety, efficacy, and consumer confidence. Overall, nutraceuticals represent a dynamic and evolving sector poised to complement conventional medicine and promote sustainable global health.

17.0 Acknowledgment

We would like to express our sincere gratitude to the Government College of Pharmacy, Karad, Maharashtra, for providing us with the facilities, guidance, and academic environment that made this review work possible. We are deeply thankful to our respected Principal, faculty members, and mentors for their continuous encouragement, valuable suggestions, and support throughout the preparation of this work.

We also acknowledge the contributions of various researchers and authors whose studies have provided the foundation for this review on nutraceuticals.

18.0 REFERENCES

1. Caraka Samhita. 700 BCE. Chikitsa sthana. Chapter 1. Parts 1–4 on rasayana. Edited and translated to English by Sharma, P. V. Varanasi, India: Choukhamba Prakashan.
2. Nasri H., Baradaran A., Shirzad H., Rafieian-Kopaei M. New Concepts in Nutraceuticals as Alternative for Pharmaceuticals. *Int. J. Prev. Med.*, 2014; 5: 1487–1499. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]

3. Caramia G., Silvi S. Probiotics: From the Ancient Wisdom to the Actual Therapeutical and Nutraceutical Perspective. In: Malago J.J., Koninkx J.F.J.G., Marinsek-Logar R., editors. Probiotic Bacteria and Enteric Infections: Cytoprotection by Probiotic Bacteria. Springer; Dordrecht, The Netherlands, 2011; 3–37. [Google Scholar]
4. Ried K. Garlic Lowers Blood Pressure in Hypertensive Individuals, Regulates Serum Cholesterol, and Stimulates Immunity: An Updated Meta-analysis and Review. *J. Nutr.*, 2016; 146: 389S–396S. doi: 10.3945/jn.114.202192. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
5. Das L, Bhaumik E, Raychaudhuri U, Chakraborty R. (2011) Role of nutraceuticals in human health. , *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 49(2): 173-183.
6. Puri V, Nagpal M, Singh I, Singh M, Dhingra GA, Huanbutta K, Dheer D, Sharma A, Sangnim T. A Comprehensive Review on Nutraceuticals: Therapy Support and Formulation Challenges. *Nutrients.*, 2022 Nov 3; 14(21): 4637. doi: 10.3390/nu14214637. PMID: 36364899; PMCID: PMC9654660.
7. Madhura Jadhav*, Tejaswini Gurud, Prof. Swapnil G. Kale. The comprehensive review on Nutraceuticals: Introduction, History, classification, formulations, growth and development, Apr 2024; 1745-1757.
8. Lipi Das, Eshani Bhaumik, Utpal Raychaudhuri and Runu Chakraborty. Role of nutraceuticals in human health. *J Food Sci Technol*, 2012; 49(2): 173–183. DOI 10.1007/s13197-011-0269-4 <https://www.crchealth.com/types-of-therapy/nutraceutical-therapy/>
9. AlAli, M., Alqubaisy, M., Aljaafari, M. N., AlAli, A. O., Baqais, L., Molouki, A., Abushelaibi, A., Lai, K. S., & Lim, S. E. (2021). Nutraceuticals: Transformation of Conventional Foods into Health Promoters/Disease Preventers and Safety Considerations. *Molecules* (Basel, Switzerland), 26(9): 2540. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26092540>
10. AlAli M, Alqubaisy M, Aljaafari MN, et al. Nutraceuticals: Transformation of Conventional Foods into Health Promoters/Disease Preventers and Safety Considerations. *Molecules*, 2021; 26(9): 2540. Published 2021 Apr 27. doi:10.3390/molecules26092540
11. Al-Sheraji S.H., Ismail A., Manap M.Y., Mustafa S., Yusof R.M., Hassan F.A. Prebiotics as Functional Foods: A review. *J. Funct. Foods*, 2013; 5: 1542–1553. doi: 10.1016/j.jff.2013.08.009. [DOI] [Google Scholar]
12. Caetano B.F.R., De Moura N.A., Almeida A.P.S., Dias M.C., Sivieri K., Barbisan L.F. Yacon (*Smallanthus sonchifolius*) as a Food Supplement: Health-Promoting Benefits of Fructooligosaccharides. *Nutrients*, 2016; 8: 436. doi: 10.3390/nu8070436. [DOI] [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]

13. Petiwala S.M., Johnson J.J. Diterpenes from rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis*): Defining their potential for anti-cancer activity. *Cancer Lett.*, 2015; 367: 93–102. doi: 10.1016/j.canlet.2015.07.005. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
14. Gupta S.V., Pathak Y.V. *Advances in Nutraceutical Applications in Cancer: Recent Research Trends and Clinical Applications*. CRC Press LLC; Milton, UK: 2019.
15. Shukla Y., George J. Combinatorial strategies employing nutraceuticals for cancer development. *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.*, 2011; 1229: 162–175. doi: 10.1111/j.1749-6632.2011.06104.x. [DOI] [PubMed]
16. Srinivasan K. Antioxidant Potential of Spices and Their Active Constituents. *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr.*, 2014; 54: 352–372. doi: 10.1080/10408398.2011.585525. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
17. Krajka-Kuźniak V., Szafer H., Ignatowicz E., Adamska T., Baer-Dubowska W. Beetroot juice protects against N-nitrosodiethylamine-induced liver injury in rats. *Food Chem. Toxicol.*, 2012; 50: 2027–2033. doi: 10.1016/j.fct.2012.03.062. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
18. Dav G., Santilli F., Patrono C. Nutraceuticals in Diabetes and Metabolic Syndrome. *Cardiovasc. Ther.*, 2010; 28: 216–226. doi: 10.1111/j.1755-5922.2010.00179.x. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
19. Holesh JE, Aslam S, Martin A. Physiology, Carbohydrates. [Updated 2023 May 12]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK459280/>
20. Singh, S. et al. (2024). Emerging Trends in Nutraceutical Research: Role of Minerals. In: Bashir, K., Jan, K., Ahmad, F.J. (eds) *Functional Foods and Nutraceuticals: Chemistry, Health Benefits and the Way Forward*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-59365-9_5
21. A. Rana, V. Kumar, N. K. Taneja, and T. Dhewa, in *Functional Foods of the Future*, ed. V. K. Gupta, M. Sharma, S. Gaur, and R. C. Kuhad, Royal Society of Chemistry, 2025, vol. 44, ch. 10, pp. 206-226.22. Jha SK, Roy P, Chakrabarty S (2021) Nutraceuticals of Pharmaceutical Importance and Their Applications. *Int J Drug Dev & Res.*,13(S3): 002.
22. Caleja C, Ribeiro A, Barreiro MF, Ferreira ICFR. Phenolic Compounds as Nutraceuticals or Functional Food Ingredients. *Curr Pharm Des.*, 2017; 23(19): 2787-2806. doi: 10.2174/1381612822666161227153906. PMID: 28025943.
23. Jha SK, Roy P, Chakrabarty S (2021) Nutraceuticals of Pharmaceutical Importance and Their Applications. *Int J Drug Dev & Res.*, 13(S3): 002.

24. Sut S., Baldan V., Faggian M., Peron G., Dall'Acqua S. Nutraceuticals, a new challenge for medicinal chemistry. *Curr. Med. Chem.*, 2016; 23: 3198–3223. doi: 10.2174/0929867323666160615104837. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
25. Augustin M.A., Sanguansri L. Challenges in developing delivery systems for food additives, nutraceuticals and dietary supplements. In: Garti N., McClements D.J., editors. *Encapsulation Technologies and Delivery Systems for Food Ingredients and Nutraceuticals*. Woodhead Publishing Ltd.; Sawston, UK, 2012; 19–48. [Google Scholar]
26. Puri V, Nagpal M, Singh I, Singh M, Dhingra GA, Huanbutta K, Dheer D, Sharma A, Sangnim T. A Comprehensive Review on Nutraceuticals: Therapy Support and Formulation Challenges. *Nutrients*, 2022 Nov 3; 14(21): 4637. doi: 10.3390/nu14214637. PMID: 36364899; PMCID: PMC9654660.
27. Papaspyridi L.M., Aligiannis N., Christakopoulos P., Skaltsounis A.L., Fokialakis N. Production of bioactive metabolites with pharmaceutical and nutraceutical interest by submerged fermentation of *Pleurotus ostreatus* in a batch stirred tank bioreactor. *Procedia Food Sci.*, 2011; 1: 1746–1752. doi: 10.1016/j.profoo.2011.09.257. [DOI] [Google Scholar].
28. Kaliappan I, Kammalla AK, Ramasamy MK, Agrawal A, Dubey GP. Emerging need of pharmacokinetics in Ayurvedic system of medicine. *International Journal of Research in Ayurveda and Pharmacy*, 2013 Sep; 4(5): 647-51.
29. Dima, C., Assadpour, E., Dima, S., & Jafari, S. M. (2020). Bioavailability of nutraceuticals: Role of the food matrix, processing conditions, the gastrointestinal tract, and nanodelivery systems. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety*. doi:10.1111/1541-4337.12547.
30. Dima, C., Assadpour, E., Dima, S., & Jafari, S. M. (2020a). Bioactive loaded nanocarriers for functional foods: From designing to bioavailability. *Current Opinion in Food Science*, 33: 21–29. doi: 10.1016/j.cofs.2019.11.006.
31. Doogue MP, Polasek TM. The ABCD of clinical pharmacokinetics. *Ther Adv Drug Saf.*, 2013 Feb; 4(1): 5-7. doi: 10.1177/ 2042098612469335.
32. Price G, Patel DA. Drug Bioavailability. [Updated 2023 Jul 30]. In: *StatPearls* [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK557852/>
33. Olivares-Morales A, Hatley OJ, Turner D, Galetin A, Aarons L, Rostami-Hodjegan A. The use of ROC analysis for the qualitative prediction of human oral bioavailability from animal data. *Pharm Res.*, 2014 Mar; 31(3): 720-30. doi:10.1007/s11095-013-1193-2.

34. Dima, C., Assadpour, E., Dima, S., & Jafari, S. M. (2020b). Bioavailability and bioaccessibility of food bioactive compounds; overview and assessment by in vitro methods. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety*, 19(6): 2862–2884. doi:10.1111/1541-4337.12623
35. Fernández-García E, Carvajal-Lérida I, Pérez-Gálvez A. In vitro bioaccessibility assessment as a prediction tool of nutritional efficiency. *Nutrition research*, 2009 Nov 1; 29(11): 751-60.
36. McClements DJ, Li F, Xiao H. The nutraceutical bioavailability classification scheme: classifying nutraceuticals according to factors limiting their oral bioavailability. *Annual review of food science and technology*, 2015 Apr 10; 6(1): 299-327.
37. Ronis MJJ, Pedersen KB, Watt J. Adverse Effects of Nutraceuticals and Dietary Supplements. *Annu Rev Pharmacol Toxicol*, 2018; 58: 583-601. doi:10.1146/annurev-pharmtox-010617-052844
38. Agu, Peter & Afiukwa, Celestine & Orji, Obasi & Ezeh, Ernest & Ofoke, Ifeanyi & Ogbu, Celestine & Ugwuja, Emmanuel & Aja, Patrick. (2023). Molecular docking as a tool for the discovery of molecular targets of nutraceuticals in diseases management. *Scientific Reports*. 13. 10.1038/s41598-023-40160-2.
39. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/revolutionizing-nutraceutical-research-development-ai-suthar-phd-tvjff?utm>
40. <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/nutraceuticals-market#:~:text=The%20aging%20global%20population%2C%20particularly,trend%20powering%20the%20industry%20forward>
41. <https://www.fortunebusinessinsights.com/nutraceuticals-market-102530>
42. Archana A. Bele, Anubha Khale. An approach to a Nutraceutical. *Research J. Pharm. and Tech*, 6(10): October 2013; Page 1161-1164.
43. <https://biothrivesciences.com/dietary-supplement-manufacturing/the-future-of-nutraceuticals-emerging-trends-and-innovations-in-health/>
44. Chauhan B, Kumar G, Kalam N (2013) Current concepts and prospects of herbal nutraceutical: a review. *J Adv Pharm Technol Res.*, 4(1): 4.
45. Sharma S, Bano A, Pathak N (2019) Pre- and probiotics: using functional foods in the fight against microbial resistance to antibiotics. *Antibacterial drug discovery to combat MDR*, 978-981-13- 9870-4, 459963_1_En, (18).